

LANGUAGE LEARNING ACTIVITIES AND ORAL LANGUAGE PERFORMANCE OF THE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

It is believed that the communicative language teaching approach is one of the most effective methods to keep away from the weaknesses of the traditional English teaching method in developing students' oral language ability. Using language learning activities, which is communicative in essence, are often considered effective in developing students' oral performance. This study attempted to find out the effectiveness of language learning activities in enhancing the oral language performance of grade ten learners in Southville IV National High School under the sixth district, Division of Santa Rosa City for the school year 2020 - 2021. This research study used pre-experimental approach because they provide little or no control of extraneous variables in the form of one-group pretest-posttest design. The researcher wants to determine the effectiveness of using language learning activities in improving students' oral language performance. The impact is assessed by providing a specific treatment. The vital tool used in the study is lesson exemplars on argumentation reflecting the most essential learning competencies for grade 10 English in the third quarter. These lesson exemplars have exposed the students to language learning activities (line dialogue, communicative game, minute paper and playing cards) mainly communicative and interactive in essence. The researcher has administered the lessons through virtual platform (G-meet) within a period of 5 weeks. The researcher has also chosen argumentative speech as piece for both pre and post assessment. The raters together with the researcher have been guided by the speech delivery rubric in assessing student's oral performance in terms of eye contact, volume/projection, and pacing/rate. This study further explored the pivotal role played by the language learning intervention in enabling the learners to improve their oral performance. The language learning activities enabled the students to use eye contact, volume/projection and rate/pacing properly in expressing themselves orally through speech delivery. In this study dependent sample t-test was applied to analyze the significant difference between the mean scores on pre-assessment and post-assessment of the respondents in oral language performance in general. The results on pre-assessment and post-assessment in over-all oral language performance revealed that utilization of language learning activities such as line dialog, communicative game, minute paper and playing cards significantly improved the learner's oral language performance. The study revealed two important findings. First, the empirical results of the research found that language learning activities (Line dialog, playing cards, minute paper, and communicative game) were effective on learning basic oral presentation concepts. Second, learners' oral language performance was improved. Based on

these findings, the study offers some recommendations for both students and teachers to improve the students' oral presentation skills.

Keywords: Language Learning Activities, Communicative, Interactive, Line Dialogue, Minute Paper, Playing Cards, Oral Language Performance.